

HOW DO FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS DEAL WITH HUMAN RESOURCE RISKS?

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Abstract. *Human resource (HR) risks remain underexplored in both academic research and regulatory practice, despite their growing recognition as a key source of systemic risk in the financial sector. This study investigates the relationships between HR risk and other major risk domains, including Operational, Legal, AML, ESG, Strategic, and Governance risks. A systematic literature review of Scopus-indexed studies (2014–2025) identified only 22 relevant works, with just two briefly addressing staff-related risks and no established modeling framework. Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), expert data from five EU financial institutions were analyzed. The results show that HR-specific threats explain 85.2% of the variance in HR risk, compared to only 12% in models using general threats. Findings suggest HR risk is tightly connected to governance, compliance, and organizational culture. Regulators and institutions should establish dedicated metrics, proactive controls, and strategic integration to mitigate HR risk.*

Keywords: *Financial Institutions; Human Resource Risk; PLS-SEM; Systematic Literature Review; Risk Management; Risks Interdependence*

JEL Classification: G32, M12, G21, G34

Introduction

The contemporary environment of financial sector is highly regulated and complex, and it requires the serious measures for supporting the existing legal acts and mitigating existing

risks.(Laeven & Levine, 2009; Mursalov, 2021; Rastogi, Sharma, Pinto & Bhimavarapu, 2022; Usman, Griffiths & Alam, 2024) Best practices of governance of financial institutions and proper risk management allow meeting these challenging tasks.(Abid, Gull, Hussain & Nguyen, 2021; Brandis, Dzombeta, Colomo-Palacios & Stantchev, 2019; Cernisevs, Popova & Cernisevs, 2023b; Mohd-Sanusi, Mat-Isa, Ahmad-Bakhtiar, Mat-Jusoh & Tarjo, 2022)

Risk management has traditionally focused on financial, credit, market, and operational risks. However, in recent years, the role of human capital as both a critical asset and a potential source of systemic vulnerability has gained increasing recognition. Human resource (HR) risks, encompassing employees' misconduct, inadequate talent management, poor organizational culture, high turnover, lack of skilled personnel, failures in leadership, and so on, have emerged as pivotal contributors to institutional instability and operational failure (Basel Committee, 2025; International Monetary Fund, 2014; Mawutor, 2014).

The importance of HR risks is highlighted by numerous high-profile scandals in the financial sector, such as the LIBOR manipulation, rogue trading incidents, compliance failures linked to inadequate training or ethical lapses (for instance, the JPMorgan "London Whale" case (Zeissler & Metrick, 2019) Libor Scandal (Batten, Lončarski & Szilagyi, 2022; Huan, Previts & Parbonetti, 2023) Wells Fargo Fake Accounts Scandal (Eradiri, Adebayo, Ogieriakhi, Egbuna & Adebayo, 2025; Hurley & Hurley, 2020) Enron Scandal (BALOĞLU & ÇAKALI, 2023; Boddy, 2023) AIG Financial Products Collapse (Buchholtz & Lawson, 2021; Wiggins, Lawson, Kelly, Engbith & Metrick, 2021) Danske Bank Money Laundering Scandal (Bjerregaard & Kirchmaier, 2019; Makarychev & Sazonov, 2025). These events illustrate that human behavior, whether intentional or due to negligence, can trigger significant financial losses, reputational damage, and regulatory sanctions (Sobanova & Kudinska, 2023). As noted by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, "people risk" is now recognized as a core component of operational risk, requiring systematic identification, monitoring, and mitigation (Basel Committee, 2025; Mawutor, 2014).

Moreover, HR risks are not isolated; they are deeply interdependent with other risk categories. For instance, a shortage of skilled compliance officers can amplify legal and regulatory risks (Cernisevs et al., 2023b; Cernisevs, Popova & Cernisevs, 2023a; Kalimoldayev, Popova, Cernisevs & Popovs, 2025). Poor leadership or toxic organizational culture may impair decision-making, thereby exacerbating strategic and operational risks (Melnyk et al., 2024; Zeissler & Metrick, 2019). Similarly, inadequate training and supervision increase the likelihood of errors and fraud, directly impacting operational resilience.

Furthermore, digital transformation and automation in financial services have shifted the demand toward specialized skills in data analytics, cybersecurity, and AI governance (Babenko et al., 2025; Mylnyk et al., 2024; Popova & Petrov, 2020; Yakubova, Manankova, Tashev & Sadikova, 2020), making talent acquisition and retention even more critical. Failure to adapt HR strategies to these evolving needs can result in capability gaps that compromise risk management frameworks.

However, if to consider the scientific literature on risk management in the financial sector, it becomes evident that human resource (HR) risks are significantly underrepresented as a distinct and systematic area of study. While there is a substantial body of research on leadership styles, corporate social responsibility, employee engagement, and HR service delivery models, few academic works explicitly isolate HR-related risks. They consider behavioral biases (Molina-García, Diéguez-Soto, Galache-Laza & Campos-Valenzuela, 2023), ethical lapses, poor talent management, or cultural toxicity as core components of financial risk frameworks, but nor see their interconnection with other risks of financial institutions. As noted by (Gabaix, 2025), human judgment and decision-making are central to financial outcomes. This gap suggests a disconnect between theoretical risk modeling and the practical reality of financial institutions. Moreover, in the studies that do incorporate HR risks, they are often subsumed within broader categories such as operational risk or governance risk, and their relative weight is minimized in quantitative models. For instance, in enterprise risk management (ERM) (Anton & Nucu, 2020; Nocco & Stulz, 2022) frameworks based on Basel II and III, do not mention the HR factor or typically classify HR-related failures under "people risk" within operational

risk. This marginalization implies that HR risks are seen as inevitable by-products rather than manageable exposures, despite their proven impact. Furthermore, the tendency to treat HR risks only as after-the-fact consequences of misconduct rather than as preventable, measurable, and manageable risks reflects a reactive rather than proactive approach in both academia and practice.

Therefore, the systematic literature review is required to understand whether the scholars write about the human resource risks or not, and how they determine these risks.

Then, another area requires the great attention. The risks framework received practical attention of regulating authorities only in year 2014. From that time the authorities somehow have determined the way of considering AML, ICT and ESG risks; Basel II and III also considered Capital Adequacy and Financial risks. However, even for these risks the authorities determined only several threats which should be considered by financial institution, adding, that “other factors” should also be taken into account. The regulations (EBA, 2024; European Parliament and of the Council. Lovforslag 2022; Lovforslag 2025; Lovforslag 2018) describing the AML, ICT and ESG risks, mention several points, which can be referred to Human Safety or Human Resource Risks. The Human Resource risks are not described separately. The only possible way to estimate Human Resource Risk is to consider the threats described used in the framework of AML, ICT and ESG risks. Therefore, the financial institutions use the same threats for determining the HR risks, as for other risks. Moreover, the “other factors” are also waiting for detailed explanation (Ashraf & Badi, 2025; Irfan & Rahman, 2025), which is in full correspondence with view of Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (Committee, 2013) that the risk frameworks lack dedicated metrics, stress testing, or predictive analytics.

According to the above said, there is a pressing need for more targeted scientific inquiry into HR-specific risks in the financial sector, including their identifying factors, measurement, and mitigation. Therefore, the second task for literature review is to discover, whether the scientists use the specific determinants for HR risks and how they apply them. The methodological approach to systematic literature review is provided in Methodology section.

The goal of this study is to develop a comprehensive model of human resource risks interdependencies on the basis of specified factors.

The results obtained from systematic literature review allow stating the significant systemic gap in the academic research devoted to the HR risks. Despite the increasing complexity of financial systems, scientific literature continues to underemphasize human resource risks as a distinct and measurable category. Most studies either ignore HR completely or treat HR as a secondary or soft factor, or focus on consumers rather than employees. As real-world scandals (e.g., Wells Fargo, LIBOR, Danske Bank) show, employees’ behavior often triggers the financial failure; yet it is still ignored as a full-fledge human resource risk in scientific research

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Literature review

Systematic literature review is based on such studies as (Butler, Yigitcanlar & Paz, 2021; Kalimoldayev et al., 2025; Popova & Popovs, 2023; Wee & Banister, 2016).

The inclusion criteria are as follows: the study should be full-text available in open access, in English, the publication should be included in Scopus database. the time span of publications was from 2014 to August 2025. Year 2014 was chosen as a year when the risks framework used by contemporary financial institutions appear. The Scopus was used since it is the database with the largest number of articles on social and economic area, and studies indexed in Scopus are usually indexed in WoS as well, and search in Scopus only allows avoiding doubling (Falagas, Pitsouni, Malietzis & Pappas, 2008; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Popova & Popovs, 2023; Vujković, Ravšelj, Umek & Aristovnik, 2022). The search was based on Boolean approach and included the following operators:

Figure 1. Search Boolean operators.

Further the methodology presupposes the more detailed study of abstracts, then full-text articles, snow-balling procedure and detailed analysis of the relevant articles. In this case all these stages were ignored since the obtained results do not allow the further analysis: Boolean search showed shocking 0 result.

2.2. PLS-SEM

The authors use PLS-SEM as the most appropriate tool for constructing the model for exploratory and confirmatory studies under the condition of comparatively small sample of data. Another important factor influencing the choice of PLS-SEM is absence of requirement towards the standard data distribution (Cernisevs et al., 2023b, 2023a; W. Chin et al., 2020; W. W. Chin, 1998; Dash & Paul, 2021; Joseph F. Hair et al., 2021; Joseph F Hair, Risher, Sarstedt & Ringle, 2019; Popova & Zagulova, 2022).

The model is traditionally assessed for two domains – inner and outer models. Outer model employs PLS algorithm and allows estimating how well the variables are constructed. The inner model uses bootstrapping algorithm and shows how the variables are interconnected.(Abdul-Rahman, Rahman & Alias, 2024; Aburumman, Omar, Al Shbail & Aldoghan, 2023; Khudzari, Haron, Ayer & Rahman, 2025; Memon et al., 2021)

The main interest of the study is in inner model; however, if the outer model is of low quality, the relationships between the variables will be not relevant. Therefore, the whole set of indicators of both inner and outer model should be estimated. Table 1 shows the reference values for the indicators of outer model, Table 2 – for inner model, and Table 3 allows estimation of the entire model. The most comprehensive basis for the evaluating the models are presented in (Popova & Zagulova, 2022). However, the reference values are also shown be (W. Chin et al., 2020; W. W. Chin, 1998; Joe F. Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2011; Wong, 2013) and many others.

The Materials and Methods should be described with sufficient details to allow others to replicate and build on the published results. Please note that the publication of your manuscript implicates that you must make all materials, data, computer code, and protocols associated with the publication available to readers. Please disclose at the submission stage any restrictions on the availability of materials or information. New methods and protocols should be described in detail while well-established methods can be briefly described and appropriately cited.

Research manuscripts reporting large datasets that are deposited in a publicly available database should specify where the data have been deposited and provide the relevant accession numbers. If the accession numbers have not yet been obtained at the time of submission, please state that they will be provided during review. They must be provided prior to publication.

Table I. Reference values for estimating outer model

Factor	Measure	Reference Values
Item reliability	Indicators loadings (IL)	>0.70 (Ned Kock, 2015)

		>0.50 (Joseph F Hair et al., 2019; Nunnally, 1978)
Convergent validity	Composite reliability (CR)	>0.40 (Gorsuch, 1988) >0.80 (Peter, 1979) >0.70 (in exploratory research 0.60 to 0.70 is considered acceptable) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Joseph F Hair et al., 2019; Nunnally, 1978; Wong, 2013)
	Average variance extracted (AVE)	>0.50 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) AVE >0.5 and CR <0.6 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981)
Discriminant validity	Fornell and Larcker (F&L) Cross-loadings Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT)	confidence intervals should not include a value of 1; theoretically distinct constructs < 0.85; (Ab Hamid, Sami & Mohamad Sidek, 2017) for analogous constructs < 0.90 (Joe Hair, Hollingsworth, Randolph & Chong, 2017; Henseler, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2015)
Degree of multicollinearity	Variance inflation factor (VIF)	<3.3 (Mateos-Aparicio, 2011; Ringle, Sarstedt, Mitchell & Gudergan, 2020)
The probability of the null hypothesis	p-value	p < 0.05 (Joseph F Hair et al., 2019; Henseler et al., 2015)

Table II. Reference values for estimating inner model

Factor	Measure	Reference Values
Coefficient of determination	R ²	Higher value is preferred: 0.67 substantial, 0.33 average, 0.19 weak (W. W. Chin, 1998; Joseph Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014)
Standardized path coefficients	Beta (β)	Values from -1 to +1. (Joe F. Hair et al., 2011; Joe Hair et al., 2017)
Significance of the paths coefficients	p-values	p < 0.05 82 (Joseph F Hair et al., 2019; Ringle et al., 2020)
Effect size	f ²	0.35 (strong effects)

Predictive relevance	Q ²	0.15 (moderate)
		0.02 (weak)(Cohen, 2013; Joseph Hair et al., 2014)
		>0.5 (W. W. Chin, 1998)

Table III. Reference values for estimating outer model

Factor	Measure	Reference Values
Number of iterations	Stop criterion	<10 (Joe F. Hair et al., 2011)
		Maximum: 300 (RINGLE, 2005)
	Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	<0.08; (Henseler et al., 2015)
	<i>Bentler and Bonett Index: normed fit index (NFI)</i>	Confidence Intervals >0.09, the closer NFI to 1, the better the match

The model is implemented in SmartPLS 4.0 software. The values of threats for the variables were estimated by board of experts, representing five financial institutions. These financial institutions operate in the European Union, they are regulated by financial authorities, deal with payment operations. The experts are risk officers of these financial institutions.

2.3. Conceptual model of the research.

The goal of the study is to construct the comprehensive model of human resource risk. The authors use the standard set of risks within the financial sector: Operational, Governance, Strategic, Legal, ESG and AML risks. The model should see how these constructs influence Human Resource Risk. Fig. 2 represents the conceptual model of the research.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of the research.

The following hypotheses were set

- H1 Strategic Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.
- H2 Operational Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.
- H3 Governance Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.
- H4 Legal Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.
- H5 AML Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.
- H6 ESG Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.

The hypotheses were tested in SmartPLS 4.0 software. The authors developed two models of Human Resource Risk. The first model uses short list of threats usually used for estimation of this risk. The second model uses enhanced list of factors.

2.4. Human Resource Risk Variable

The central variable of the model is Human Resource Risk. To construct this variable the authors used two sets of factors.

First set employs the threats which are used traditionally for determining the Human Resource Risk. However, the obtained model is of very poor quality. Therefore, we used the second set of threats, which is significantly bigger compared to the first one. The full sets of factors are presented in Appendix A. Table 4 presents the sample of factors lists for Model 1 and Model 2.

Table IV. This is a table. Tables should be placed in the main text near to the first time they are cited.

1st Set of Factors (Model 1)	2nd Set of Factors (Model 2)
Air pollution	data
1st Set of Factors (Model 1)	2nd Set of Factors (Model 2)
Air pollution	Air pollution
Environmental accidents	Environmental accidents
Earthquake	Earthquake
Flooding	Flooding
Hurricane	Hurricane
Lightning	Lightning
Heat waves	Heat waves
Fire	Fire
Water scarcity - Lack or insufficient supply of water	Water scarcity - Lack or insufficient supply of water
Public policy change-pollution control regulations	Public policy change- pollution control regulations
Shifting sentiment - Changes in consumer preference for certain products	-Shifting sentiment - Changes in consumer preference for certain products
	+
	Failure to meet sectoral or institutional greenhouse gas reduction targets
	Dependency on scarce or high-emission resources leading to operational and supply chain disruptions
	Increased operational costs from carbon pricing, taxes, or stricter emission standards
	Non-compliance with social-related disclosure and reporting requirements
	Weak board oversight of social and environmental risks and lack of integration in corporate governance
	Greenwashing or misrepresentation of social and environmental performance in reports and marketing
	Lack of transparent social and environmental reporting and inadequate internal data quality
	Obsolescence of business model or products due to regulatory or market shift toward low-carbon economy

Sudden portfolio devaluation due to sectoral exposure to carbon-intensive industries
 Loss of access to funding or investment due to poor social and environmental ratings
 High concentration in sectors vulnerable to social and environmental risks (fossil fuels, high water use, deforestation)
 Counterparties failing to adapt to ESG regulations or market changes
 Supply chain disruption due to counterparties' social and environmental non-compliance
and so on (see Appendix A)

These factors, estimated by experts, were used for constructing the Human Resource Risk variable.

3. Results

3.1. Literature Review

The results are absolutely disappointing. The search discovered only 22 articles. However, after more detailed investigation of abstract, it was discovered that only 9 of them relate to financial sector, and only 2 articles somehow mention the performance of staff, but still do not include the framework of HR risks. Therefore, it is possible to state the academic lacuna on HR risks. Despite the increasing complexity of financial systems, scientific literature continues to underemphasize human resource risks as a distinct and measurable category. Most studies either ignore HR completely or treat HR as a secondary or soft factor, or focus on consumers rather than employees. This systemic gap in academic and practical risk management requires attention. The development of Human Risk Model is urgent and important practical and scientific task.

3.2. Development of Model 1 based on standard set of threats

The estimated values of threats from set 1 (see Table 4) were used for creating the PLS-SEM model in SmartPLS 4.0 software. Human Resource Risk is used as a dependent variable, while Strategic, Operational Governance, Legal, AML and ESG risks as independent constructs.

The obtained model is presented in Fig.3

Figure 3. Human Resource Risk Model 1

As we see, the model explains only about 12% Human Resource Risk. If to refer to model estimations, all the indicators of assessment of outer and inner models are of high quality, the dependencies are shown in a correct way. If to refer to the idea that the risks of financial institutions are interconnected (Al Kilani et al., 2023; Cernisevs et al., 2023a, 2023b; Kalimoldayev et al., 2025; Popova, 2021; Thair et al., 2023), this model does not support the idea of the scholars. However, it contradicts the logic. The authors presuppose that the issue is not the lack of interconnectedness, which is supported statistically by the studies, for example, by (Cernisevs et al., 2023a, 2023b). In these studies, Human Resource Risks is also isolated, not interconnected with other risks. Therefore,

the problem issue is the variable Human Resource Risk. If to see the list of threats which are estimated in Model 1 (Table 4, column 1), we see that these threats assume that human resource will suffer due to some negative events – nature disasters or some negative changes in organisation. However, if to see the nature of human resource, significantly more factors can influence the risky situation. We have decided to try to add the threat factors which can influence the Human Resource Risk (the new set of threat factors is partially presented in Table 4, column 2, and the full set of threat factors is shown in Appendix A). Therefore, the construct “Human Resource Risk” was changed significantly, while other variables were not changed. The resulted model is presented in Fig.4.

Figure 4. Human Resource Risk Model 2

Blue circles are variables. Yellow boxes are factors forming these variables. The arrows between variables (blue circles) and their factors (yellow boxes) show the interconnectedness, and values are the values of loading of each factor, showing its importance for the variable. The arrows between variables show the direction of dependence. In this model we test the impacts of variables on Human Resource Risk – the arrows to the Human Resource Risk variable show these impacts. The values on the arrows are bettas. The value in the center of Human Resource variable is coefficient of determination R^2 .

The second model is absolutely different. It explains 85.2% of Human Resource Risk. The quality of outer and inner models should be tested via the specific functions of SmartPLS software. First, we test the outer model to understand that the variables employed in this model are of high quality and they can really represent the risks.

To begin with, we see that the factors of each variable are of significant importance for these variables, which is demonstrated by the loadings. The loadings are very high, supporting the idea that the constituent parts of the variables were chosen correctly.

We apply testing the construct reliability and validity to see the internal consistency of the constructs (see Table 5)

Table V. Construct reliability and validity indicators.

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho a)	Composite reliability (rho c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
AML	0.841	0.961	0.918	0.736
ESG	0.988	0.996	0.991	0.955
Human resource	0.983	0.983	0.987	0.937
Legal	0.924	0.930	0.944	0.774
Operational	0.895	0.906	0.924	0.709
Strategy	0.922	0.925	0.944	0.775

As we see, all the values are of high quality. The constructs' reliability is proven. Next step is testing discriminant validity. We demonstrate only one method of testing the discriminant validity

(see Table 6), which is the most strict one – HTMT (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). Nevertheless, other two methods of testing the discriminant validity - Fornell and Larcker (F&L) and Cross-loadings also demonstrate great quality of the outer model.

Table VI. Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	AML	ESG	Human resource	Legal	Operational	Strategy
AML						
ESG	0.232					
Human resource	0.307	0.120				
Legal	0.313	0.098	0.663			
Operational	0.352	0.309	0.741	0.414		
Strategy	0.126	0.054	0.619	0.314	0.490	

Multicollinearity was tested with VIF, and the quality of the model was supported. The values of p for all variables are below 0.05. The quality of the outer model is proven.

The high quality of the outer model allows testing the hypotheses. For testing hypotheses, we apply a bootstrapping algorithm, or testing the inner model. The results of this testing are presented in Table 7.

Table VII. Total effects

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
AML -> Human resource	0.152	0.152	0.026	5.959	0.000
ESG -> Human resource	0.293	0.291	0.045	6.497	0.000
Legal -> Human resource	0.337	0.336	0.034	9.829	0.000
Operational -> Human resource	0.496	0.495	0.037	13.371	0.000
Strategy -> Human resource	0.266	0.267	0.031	8.534	0.000

As we see, all the indicators are of high quality, null hypotheses are not supported. In Table 8 the results of hypothesis testing are presented.

Table VIII. Hypothesis testing results.

Hypothesis No.	Hypotheses Content	Result
H1	Strategic Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed
H2	Operational Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed
H3	Governance Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed
H4	Legal Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed
H5	AML Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed
H6	ESG Risk has significant direct impact on Human Resource Risk.	Confirmed

All the set hypotheses are supported. All the risks have significant impact on Human Resource Risk.

4. Discussion

The urgent need in the study dedicated to Human Resource Risk assessment is based on the fact that the regulatory documents require estimation of this risk and, simultaneously, lack of clear distinct comprehensive methodology for this estimation. The findings of this study reveal a serious and troubling disconnect between the real-world significance of Human Resource Risks in the financial sector and their representation in academic research.

Despite the increasing complexity of financial systems and the growing recognition by regulatory bodies such as the (Basel Committee, 2025; Committee, 2013; Mawutor, 2014) that "people risk" is a core component of operational risk, our systematic literature review uncovered a striking academic lacuna. Out of the initial search yielding only 22 articles, only two of them referenced staff performance, and none proposed a structured framework for Human Resource Risks as an independent measurable domain. This absence confirms a systemic gap: while HR-related failures frequently trigger financial scandals such as the LIBOR manipulation, Wells Fargo's fake accounts, or Danske Bank's money laundering scholars continue treating human behavior as a peripheral or residual factor rather than a central risk variable. There are a lot of studies which discover the role of Human Resource for the company performance, decision making process, leadership, ethical issues – but they are not interconnected with risk assessment.

The financial institutions usually use the threats for risks estimation based on fragmented and incomplete factors listed within the framework for estimation of AML, ICT and ESG risks. However, if to base the estimation on these factors, we receive situation when the Human Resource Risk does not have any significance in the entire system of risks of financial institutions (Cernisevs et al., 2023b, 2023a), or is not explained by the factors, as in Model 1 in this study.

This underrepresentation is particularly concerning given the interconnected nature of risks in financial institutions. As demonstrated in Model 2 of our PLS-SEM analysis, Human Resource Risk is not isolated but deeply influenced by other risk categories: Operational, Legal, AML, ESG, Strategic, and Governance risks. The model explains 85.2% of the variance in Human Resource Risks, a dramatic improvement over Model 1 (12%), which used the set of factors selected from fragmented list of factors for estimation of AML, ICT and ESG risks; it is obvious that the 1 set of factors is inappropriate for Human Resource Risk. The enhanced factor list incorporating such elements as lack of skilled personnel, poor leadership, ethical lapses, inadequate training, high turnover, and cultural toxicity (the full list of used factors is presented in Appendix A), reflects the actual drivers of Human Resource vulnerability. This supports the argument that Human Resource Risks are not independent event but constituent part of a broader scope of institutional weaknesses. For example, weak governance structures (H3) foster toxic cultures; legal risks (H4) arise from non-compliance due to undertrained staff; and AML risks (H5) are amplified by insufficient human capacity in compliance roles.

Moreover, the results align with real-world evidence: the JPMorgan "London Whale" incident was not merely a trading error but a failure of leadership, oversight, and risk culture (Zeissler & Metrick, 2019); the Wells Fargo scandal stemmed from a sales-driven culture that Human Resource failed to counterbalance with ethical training or accountability (Hurley & Hurley, 2020); and the Danske Bank case exposed how understaffed and disempowered compliance teams allowed massive money laundering to go unchecked (Bjerregaard & Kirchmaier, 2019). These are not isolated incidents of misconduct but systemic Human Resource Risk failures, yet the academic literature rarely models them as such. Instead, Human Resource Risks are often subsumed under operational risk in ERM frameworks (Anton & Nucu, 2020; Kaspereit, Lopatta, Pakhchanyan & Prokop, 2017; Leo, 2020), deprived of dedicated metrics, stress testing, or predictive analytics, as noted by the (International Monetary Fund, 2014) and (Committee, 2013).

The methodological approach from Model 1 versus Model 2 further underscores a critical issue: the way how we specify the Human Resource Risk determines whether we can measure and manage it. Model 1's failure using the limited list of threats as factors of Human Resource Risk reveals a fundamental misunderstanding of Human Resource Risk as something that "can happen to employees", rather than something emerging from human behaviour and existence as a systems. In

contrast, Model 2's success confirms that Human Resource Risk is endogenous, shaped by organizational design, leadership, culture, and competence. This shift from viewing Human Resource as a passive victim of external shocks to recognizing it as an active, dynamic risk domain is essential for modern risk management. As digital transformation increases demand for specialized skills in AI, cybersecurity, and data governance (Babenko et al., 2025; Khan & Malaika, 2021), the ability to attract, retain, and develop talent becomes a strategic risk in itself.

Finally, the regulatory landscape reflects this ambiguity. While frameworks for AML, ICT, and ESG risks exist, they mention HR-related threats only implicitly without defining a coherent HR risk taxonomy. The phrase "other factors" in regulatory guidelines (Ashraf & Badi, 2025; Irfan & Rahman, 2025) remains undefined, leaving institutions to extrapolate Human Resource Risk from fragmented cues. This lack of clarity leads to the continued use of a reactive, post-factum approach to risks in human resource management, where they are viewed as the result of failure rather than as a preventable threat.

The authors invite the scientific community and the practitioners of the financial sector to participate in discussion what other factors can be used for determining the Human Resource Risk.

5. Conclusions

The goal of the study was to develop a comprehensive model of Human Resource Risks interdependencies on the basis of specified factors.

The model was developed (Model 2), the quality of model is high.

All set hypotheses were supported. Such risks of financial institutions as Strategic, Operational, Governance, Legal, AML and ESG risks are significant for determination of Human Resource Risk.

The risk framework is highly interconnected. The change in determination of any risk will be reflected on Human Resource Risk.

This study makes three key contributions to both scientific and practical understanding of risk in the financial sector.

The authors determined the academic lacuna Confirmed. There is a severe lack of scholarly attention to Human Resource Risks as a distinct, measurable construct. Most research either ignores human factors or treats them as soft, qualitative issues in risk management models. This gap undermines the development of robust, evidence-based risk models that reflect real-world dynamics.

Human Resource Risk is an interdependent component of risk management of financial institutions. Our PLS-SEM model (Model 2) demonstrates that Human Resource Risk is significantly influenced by all major risk categories, such as Operational Risk having the strongest impact ($\beta = 0.496$), followed by Legal, ESG, Strategic, and AML risks. This confirms that Human Resource Risk is not a isolated issue but a convergent risk domain, shaped by institutional governance, culture, compliance, and strategy.

We also supported the idea about the need for a new Human Resource Risk paradigm. The concept of Human Resource Risk for financial institutions should be explicitly defined with dedicated factors (e.g., skill gaps, leadership quality, ethical climate), integrated into ERM frameworks with its own KPIs, stress tests, and dashboards, proactively managed through HR-risk collaboration, including behavioral training, ethical hiring, and whistleblower protection.

Human Resource is not just a cost or a support function; it is a core risk and resilience factor. The financial sector must move beyond treating Human Resource Risks as afterthoughts or footnotes in operational risk reports. Instead, it should consider the Human Resource Risk as a constituent part of risk management, equipped with data, models, and authority to prevent the very scandals that continue to plague the industry. Future research should build on this study by developing standardized Human Resource Risk indicators, exploring cross-institutional benchmarks, and testing interventions that strengthen the human foundation of financial stability.

The obtained results have serious practical implications for financial institution. The regulators should develop the dedicated Human Resource Risk guidelines, specifying measurable Human Resource Risk factors.

Financial Institutions operating in the industry should establish Human Resource Risk integration in risk management on the basis of more precise factors selection.

Appendix A

Table A1. This is a table caption.

Title 1	Title 2
Air pollution	Air pollution
Environmental accidents	Environmental accidents
Earthquake	Earthquake
Flooding	Flooding
Hurricane	Hurricane
Lightning	Lightning
Heat waves	Heat waves
Fire	Fire
Water scarcity - Lack or insufficient supply of water	Water scarcity - Lack or insufficient supply of water
Public policy change- pollution control regulations	Public policy change- pollution control regulations
Shifting sentiment - Changes in consumer preference for certain products	Shifting sentiment - Changes in consumer preference for certain products
	+
	Failure to meet sectoral or institutional greenhouse gas reduction targets
	Dependency on scarce or high-emission resources leading to operational and supply chain disruptions
	Increased operational costs from carbon pricing, taxes, or stricter emission standards
	Non-compliance with social-related disclosure and reporting requirements
	Weak board oversight of social and environmental risks and lack of integration in corporate governance
	Greenwashing or misrepresentation of social and environmental performance in reports and marketing
	Lack of transparent social and environmental reporting and inadequate internal data quality
	Obsolescence of business model or products due to regulatory or market shift toward low-carbon economy
	Sudden portfolio devaluation due to sectoral exposure to carbon-intensive industries
	Loss of access to funding or investment due to poor social and environmental ratings
	High concentration in sectors vulnerable to social and environmental risks (fossil fuels, high water use, deforestation)
	Counterparties failing to adapt to social and environmental regulations or market changes
	Supply chain disruption due to counterparties' ESG non-compliance
	Slips, trips, and falls due to inadequate housekeeping or maintenance.

Falling objects or unsecured equipment
Unsafe storage of materials or hazardous substances
Inadequate fire safety equipment or blocked emergency exits.
Poor ergonomics leading to repetitive strain injuries or musculoskeletal disorders
Exposure to loud noise causing hearing damage
Exposure to vibration, radiation, or other physical hazards.
Electrical hazards from faulty wiring or equipment
Mechanical hazards from machinery without proper guarding.
Exposure to hazardous chemicals, fumes, or dust.
Confined space entry without proper safety measures.
Mould, pests, or other bio-contaminants in the workplace.
Inadequate sanitation or waste management facilities
Employees not trained in safe work procedures.
Lack of first-aid trained staff on site.
Failure to provide personal protective equipment (PPE) or train in its correct use
Insufficient safety inductions for new staff or contractors
Malfunctioning or poorly maintained safety equipment
Inadequate inspection and testing of plant and machinery
Overcrowding in work areas
Unsafe vehicle operation or traffic management in workplace areas
Inadequate verification of contractor safety records.
Toxic work environment affecting productivity and retention.
Employee dissatisfaction with leadership or management practices.
Lack of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives.
Low employee engagement or motivation.
Toxic work environment affecting productivity and retention.
Employee dissatisfaction with leadership or management practices.
Lack of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives.
Low employee engagement or motivation.
Difficulty attracting qualified candidates due to skills shortages.
High staff turnover leading to loss of institutional knowledge.
Competition from other employers offering better compensation or benefits.
Ineffective recruitment processes leading to unsuitable hires.
Overreliance on temporary/contract staff creating instability.
Skills gaps due to evolving industry, regulatory, or technological requirements.
Insufficient training or professional development opportunities.
Inadequate succession planning for key roles.
Loss of key personnel with critical expertise (“key person risk”).
Poor performance management processes
Unclear roles, responsibilities, or performance expectations
Inefficient team structures or reporting lines

Burnout due to excessive workload or poor work-life balance.
Absenteeism or presenteeism impacting operational efficiency
Non-compliance with labour laws, working time regulations, or collective agreements
Inadequate employment contracts or dispute resolution processes.
Unfair dismissal or discrimination claims.
Inequitable pay structures causing internal disputes
Unsustainable or poorly structured bonus/incentive schemes
Benefits package failing to meet employee needs
Pension and post-employment obligations becoming financially burdensome
Overstaffing leading to inefficiencies and excess costs
Understaffing causing service delivery or operational failures
Poor geographic distribution of workforce relative to business needs
Inflexible staffing models unable to adapt to seasonal or market changes
Labour union disputes or strikes
Collective bargaining conflicts
Deterioration of relationships with employee representatives
Loss of team cohesion in remote/hybrid setups
Inadequate remote working policies or support
Work-life boundaries blurred, leading to burnout
Lack of safety provisions for employees working offsite or travelling
Exposure to dangerous environments in field operations
Failure to maintain business continuity
Ineffective communication

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